

AMERICAN SOFT POWER FORECAST IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: There have been controversial debates over the topic of ‘soft power’ in the USA lately, even though some policymakers have critical view of Joseph Nye’s “soft power” term, still there is a group of scientists and American politicians who increasingly regard this concept as an indispensable tool to influence the world. The global strategy of the USA has outlined the soft power which plays vital importance in US foreign politics because of its ability to make most countries want to follow the Western values and liberal model of world order. In turn, the geopolitical shifts occurring around the globe made me research and shed some light on American soft power tools used towards Uzbekistan, its outcomes and consequences.

Keywords: soft power, International Relations, reputation, world order, civil society, culture, education, Uzbek youth.

Аннотация: В последнее время в США ведутся противоречивые дебаты по теме «мягкой силы», хотя некоторые политики критически относятся к термину «мягкой силы» Джозефа Ная, тем не менее, существует группа ученых и американских политиков, которые все больше относятся к этому вопросу как эта концепция незаменимый инструмент влияния на мир. Глобальная стратегия США обозначила мягкую силу, которая играет жизненно важную роль во внешней политике США из-за ее способности заставить большинство стран хотеть следовать западным ценностям и либеральной модели мирового порядка. В свою очередь, геополитические сдвиги, происходящие во всем мире, заставили меня изучить и пролить

некоторый свет на американские инструменты «мягкой силы», используемые в отношении Узбекистана, их результаты и последствия.

Ключевые слова: мягкая сила, Международные отношения, репутация, мировой порядок, гражданское общество, культура, образование, узбекская молодежь.

Аннотация: Сўнги пайтларда Америка Қўшма Штатларида «юмшоқ куч» мавзусида мунозарали баҳслар бўлиб ўтмоқда, гарчи баъзи сиёсатчилар Жозеф Найнинг «юмшоқ куч» атамасини танқид қилишса ҳам, бир гуруҳ олимлар ва америкалик сиёсатчилар мавжуд бўлиб, бу масалага яъни, мазкур концепция дунёга таъсир қилиш учун ажралмас восита сифатида тобора кўпроқ муносабат билдиришмоқда. АҚШнинг Глобал Стратегиясида кўпчилик мамлакатларни Ғарб қадриятлари ва дунё тартибининг либерал моделига амал қилишга ундаш қобилияти туфайли АҚШ ташқи сиёсатида муҳим роль ўйнайдиган юмшоқ куч белгилаб қўйилган. Ўз навбатида, бутун дунёда рўй бераётган геосиёсий ўзгаришлар мени Американинг Ўзбекистонга нисбатан қўлланилаётган юмшоқ куч воситалари, уларнинг натижалари ва оқибатларини ўрганишга ва биров ёритишга мажбур қилди.

Калит сўзлар: юмшоқ куч, халқаро муносабатлар, обрў, дунё тартиби, фуқаролик жамияти, маданият, таълим, ўзбек ёшлари.

Introduction

Despite the fact of being a new concept, soft power has already become the most common topic to discuss among all layers of society in Uzbekistan. Here, people approach to it from different angles, but the majority contemplate it positively as well as they admit its outweighing power over the hard power. In fact, the true, academic notion of soft power still needs further explanation or I would state raise awareness in terms of its definition through publications or mass media tools. Over the past decades, there has been growing interest in reconsidering of

“soft power” concept in the external affairs of the USA. Several politicians and scholars have raised the question whether the approach of ‘soft power’ has every grounds to believe in its preference for usage in comparison with the military-economic pressure. The world has witnessed dramatic changes in the modern world is distressed with the worsening scenario of geopolitical interests between superpowers and the emergence of threats such as Covid-19 pandemics, global warming and danger in peace. Nonetheless, despite these detrimental shifts, one can see how the USA has been working on its positive image, becoming a center of humanitarian aid for countries in need, widely declaring democratic values, and motivating other people to dream through scholarships, exchange programs, and different opportunities for youth.

Soft power of any country comes mainly from three sources: its culture; its political values, such as democracy and human rights (when it upholds them); and its policies. A government can impact others through the example of how it behaves at home, in international institutions and through its foreign policy. Thus, it appears that current US President’s mission to strengthen democracy both at home and abroad during his presidency, but outcomes remain to be witnessed, Nye argued. [1].

To emphasize one of the policy objectives of the USA states the following: the environment which enables for business in Central Asia will be transparent, open, fair, attractive to U.S. businesses, and supportive of broader development goals.

The United States is working with each Central Asian country to undertake the reforms needed to attract more foreign investment, including from American businesses. Through primary, secondary, and tertiary education reform, the United States is working to equip the next generation with the in-demand technical, managerial, English language, and critical thinking skills needed to support 21st

century economies that attract international investment and produce local entrepreneurs. [2].

In general, tremendous work and billions of dollars have been invested by the USA already, and regarding the soft power policy, the strategy of the United States is intended to advance the interests of the USA, which would make it possible to undertake a policy beneficial to Americans; secondly, in a global scale, others assert that being in the center of Central Asia, Uzbekistan is a place to maneuver for finding solutions in big geopolitical games. Moreover, American elite has concentrated on strengthening the sovereignty of Uzbekistan and is not willing to see its reintegration with other states in the region. I, personally, do not look for any challenges or support to any existing positions, my intention is to see clear picture of qualitative indicators of US soft power forecast in Uzbekistan. From my perspective, it is not measurable how it really influences and makes contribution, again to whose benefit in the end. We admit that difficulty to determine the mechanisms of influence of “soft power” on other countries to achieve the results has become even more discussed among scholars globally. Accordingly, we ought to acknowledge that it is troublesome to find an obvious association, as it occurs in the sciences, but we will attempt to find a relationship through the categories as culture and education.

METHODOLOGY

In the paper, a case-study method will be utilized, and for thorough analysis I will rely on some works of institutions as well as scholars based on comparative study, speeches and reports of US officials regarding the theme of the article. As basic resources, this paper touches upon the explorations of such American scientists as John Mearsheimer and Joseph Nye, and the reports from the Global Soft Power Index 2023 reported by Brand Finance, also includes the analysis of the Institute for International Cultural Relations at the University of Edinburgh.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Nye states that power is like the weather, and everyone depends on it and talks about it, but few understand it. Comprehensive dictionaries define power which means having the capabilities to affect the behavior of others to make those things happen. Yet, there are several ways to affect the behavior of others. One can coerce them with threats; it can be induced by payments; or one can attract or co-opt them to want that they want. If we look at the origins and genesis, the notion of “soft power” appeared in ancient times by the writings of the ancient Chinese philosopher Lao-Tzu, who claimed that the paradox is that whatever is soft will overcome whatever is rigid and stiff. Meanwhile J,Nye quotes the Italian philosopher Nicollo Machiavelli, about the significance of provoking fear to people’s minds rather than being loved, Nye notes that it is better to achieve both in our today’s globalized era.[3]. Many scholars criticize J. Nye for his vague definition of the term 'soft power' and insufficient scientific rigor of his works. Certainly, “soft power” proves to be a rather broad concept, and it seems demanding to outline its exact boundaries. The claim that the USA employs influence through soft power does not tolerate criticism, N, Ferguson argued. He claims that the culture as one of the soft power instruments does not show the full capacity to be influential in foreign affairs. American movies, art, music, and lifestyle could be appealing in the South Korea or Hong Kong, but they may have opposing viewpoints in the Middle Eastern countries due to the fact of the contradiction in mindset and religious beliefs. Therefore, the critics doubt in terms of concept’s effectiveness. [4]

Nevertheless, in return for such critical analysis, Professor Mark Neimark opposes the concept of soft power as solely a cultural and humanitarian resource of the state, He elaborates that it is measured by many other indicators of influence such as an attractive economic model, legitimate government, and even professional military force. In his study, he attempts to systematize the ways of the impact of “soft power” as follows: firstly, the economic appeal of a particular government grows the interests of the target countries. Next, the need arises to

research the progress model of the country based on its culture. As a consequence, beneficiary countries shape the information gap through specific knowledge depicting the cultural features of that prosperous nation in the end. On the whole, by creating a positive image, it is highly likely to have a rising opportunity to strengthen “soft power” policy concerning those targeted countries eventually. [5]

American scientist Dr Richard D. Hooker, Jr., argues that the soft power is blurred for being controlled, in combination with military and economic power, it has every right to be concerned as a part of the global strategy of the United States. He points out that theorists disagree on whether soft power should be regarded as part of the strategist’s arsenal. Diplomacy, for example, may be without utility when divorced from the military and economic power of the state; the artfulness of the debate can be beneficial but will not be decisive absent hard power. Overall, although the ability of soft power to influence adversary behavior for good or ill is probably incontrovertible, it is not easily deployable or even controllable. To that extent, it is an important factor that nevertheless falls outside the realm of grand strategy as traditionally understood and practiced. [6]. As a matter of fact, there are some Russian scholars, such as Alexander Naumov observe and perceive ‘soft power’ skeptically, who claim to witness the shades of ‘color and velvet revolutions’ aimed at regime change and maintain national interests. Prof. Naumov from Moscow State University emphasizes the concept as destructive technology for arranging non-violent coups. [7]. D. Suslov from Higher School of Economics in Moscow agrees that regime change policies are one element of this active component of American soft power. But he does not agree that all active components of the US “soft power” are aimed at organizing “color revolutions”, undermining state foundations and multiplying chaos. The “soft power” of the United States, its active components, is aimed at weakening those regimes that are hostile to the United States. [8]. In general, the strive of the United States to engage in soft power derives from liberal values However, the events of the last two

decades involved with the U S invasion of Iraq in 2003, the civil war in Syria, the Ukrainian crisis, withdrawal of U S troops from Afghanistan demonstrated negative attitudes and distrust of people to the liberal world order. As John Mearsheimer referred to, there is no universal agreement for the world proclaiming the best and ideal political system. One can only proclaim that liberal democracy is the most acceptable way to preserve peace, but we have to keep in mind that other people prefer different systems of governing. [9]. In my view, those cases overall might be considered as one of the main reasons of stagnation of liberal world order. People in many nations are in two minds whether to accept US values with warm hearts or not.

Regarding the academic pursuits about the American soft power policy in Uzbekistan, I have been working in collecting and analyzing the literature lately, and eager to conduct a thorough analysis of native scholars' viewpoints on this subject, Western perception, and the research of Russian scholars too. Unfortunately, not many authors have paid attention to this theme yet, and I have come across with several of them which I am going to mention their names and work. These individuals, among others, have contributed to the broader understanding of the dynamics of US soft power in Central Asia and Uzbekistan, and their works could potentially offer valuable perspectives from the region on this topic. Their research and writings shed light on the complexities of foreign influence and the interplay of cultures and powers in Uzbekistan. It is important to note that while these scholars may not have specifically focused on "US Soft Power in Uzbekistan" as a central theme, their contributions to the study of Central Asian politics, international relations, and cultural dynamics certainly contribute to the understanding of US influence in Uzbekistan and the wider region.

Soft power as novelty

As highlighted by some Uzbekistani analysts, Mirziyoyev's adherence to soft power is by far his novel undertaking. Mirziyoyev has been more receptive to soft power broadly conceived. According to Harvard University Joseph Nye Jr., soft power is "getting others to want the outcomes that you want" in that it "co-opts people rather than coerces them." It is about attraction, building trust, fostering openness and admiration, and this conception has found a receptive audience beyond the United States. Mirziyoyev has prioritised dialogue over confrontation in the region, spoken of connectivity and demonstrated openness to World Trade Organisation membership. [10].

These days, Uzbek officials highlight the necessity for cooperation with neighboring Central Asian countries in a friendlier tone with all their regional counterparts. Utilizing a soft power tool, they call for joint construction of regional power plants and fair distribution of electricity, thereby reducing the probability of regional conflicts. Sh.Mirziyoyev personally paid official visits to many neighboring countries, signed vital socio-economic agreements, including agreements on security. Many business leaders had to accompany presidential delegations. Uzbekistan welcomed the participation of representatives of main international institutions and also major foreign governments in the visits. Sh.Mirziyoyev also visited the Russian Federation, China and the United States in order to conclude trade agreements, obtain diplomatic support and maintain a security partnership. Internal reforms of the administration are aimed at presenting the country as a more attractive partner for the West, while Uzbekistan continues to deepen economic ties with Russia and China. [11]

RESULTS

The USA is implementing its cases of soft power in Central Asian countries, among which Uzbekistan is perceived as the state actively absorbing western culture, education, and lifestyle. The major courses of this strategy come down to strengthen human rights, support of the free press and democratic institutions,

development of education skills correlating with modern realities of the 21st century, which is linked to the American soft power projection altogether. [12]

It is true that 'culture' in general involves such kind of indicators as the country's influence in the form of art and music. Today in the world, it is fact that almost all nations are giving a special place as the core of soft power to the culture. There are cultural exchange programs between the United States and Uzbekistan, and they are realized through various programs, platforms, and activities, such as source centers for discovering and learning cultural and language features supported by the U S Embassy in Tashkent. Besides this, scholarships as the Fulbright Program, and the other mass cultural events. The Public Affairs Section of the U.S. Embassy in Tashkent, in cooperation with American Councils for International Education, launched the American Corners initiative throughout the Republic of Uzbekistan. The American Corners also serve as a hub for EducationUSA and provide a free consultation service to prospective undergraduate and graduate students who wish to study in the United States.

DISCUSSION

From the address by Audrey Azoulay, Director-General of UNESCO, Uzbekistan building its long tradition of fostering discussions and inspiring progress in science, in culture and education. We all know prominent names of great cities: Samarqand, Bukhara, Khiva and we all know scientific knowledge that produced by country from Avicenna, Al-Khwarizmi and Ulugh Beg and many more. This tradition of excellence is matched by an unwavering commitment to education building on this history and building on the future and especially regarding the subjects that brings us together. [13]. It has been stated over and over that education and culture play crucial role in the government policy and considered as determinants of state's efficiency, thus, ensuring quality education is vital on agenda. Prime example is the President declared 2023 as the year of "Attention to people and quality education". On August 24, 2023, the President of Uzbekistan

visited Samarkand region and mentioned the following: “We are expanding the coverage of higher education. However, not everyone chooses to study at the university. Therefore, we aim to ensure that our children start learning foreign languages and professions from school. A person who has mastered at least one profession will not be lost. He can further work on himself and improve his skills. Therefore, our goal is to create decent conditions for every young person”, the Head of state said. [14]

It is clear that universities are also one of advantageous sides of US soft power, and many American universities in QS World University Rankings hold top positions, such universities are Harvard University, MIT, Stanford, Princeton and many others. By using them, American soft power cause impulse through various academic and educational programs for Uzbek youth and allow for scholars and scientists to take part in different short-term or long-term programs which enable them to expand their outlook.

Thankfully, "El-Yurt Umid" Foundation for training specialists abroad and communicating with compatriots. Hundreds of Uzbek youth are being sent to developed countries like the USA, the UK, Japan to study and master within their sphere, and upon their return to Uzbekistan, they are contributing to the overall development of homeland.

CONCLUSION

Central Asia cannot solely be a geographical name, but also a center of commerce, tourism and culture. The goals of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev to increase GDP by 2 times can be realized if the Central Asian region attracts foreign investors and political partners, and also participates in such international organizations as the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE) and the World Trade Organization (WTO), and also under the UN Sustainable Development Goals program. The expansion of Uzbekistan’s bilateral relations with

the countries of the region and with the major world powers is the result of the “soft power” policy implementation.

I can assume, in the long-run, the products of US soft power will play a significant role in the liberalization of people’s minds. The USA will further continue to support freedom of press, democratic institutions, etc. I believe that the USA will remain as a superpower for next several decades, and Uzbekistan will continue to play a key role for America in Central Asia. Finally, one matter or notion remain clear because of this study – American soft power will be ever-present in our life, Washington will not step back in Uzbekistan and will do its best to strengthen our relationship, but I am confident with the current development and directions initiated by the president Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, we are on the right path to become developed nation in near future and will have our own say/voice in global arena.

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